

ISic3448

Funerary inscription for Asklepiades

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

limestone

Object

tabula

Editor

Jonathan Prag

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Jonathan Prag

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Autopsy

2014.10.30 Metcalfe

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Menae

Place of origin (modern)

near Mineo

Provenance

Monte Catalfaro

Coordinates

37.280623, 14.717130

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Mineo, Museo Civico Corrado
Tamburino Merlini, inventory 5194

Physical Description

Regular slab of limestone, intact on all sides

Dimensions

Height 53 cm

Width 54 cm

Depth 6 cm

Layout

three lines of Greek letters, using the full width of the stone

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

regular large quadrate letters

Letter heights:

Lines 1-3: 70-90 mm

Interlineation

Not measured: mm

Text

1. Ἀσκλη

2. πιάδη

3. χᾶϊρε

Apparatus

Text of Cordano 2005

Translation

Asklepiades, farewell!

Commentary

The text implies the vocative + salutation formula which is found several times at Mineo, and reproduced in the latin epitaph engraved on the reverse of this

stone (ISic3447 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic3447>])

Digital identifiers:

TM 644926

EDCS 70900750

Bibliography

Messina, A. 1970. Monte Catalfaro e l'identificazione di Noai. *Cronache di Archaeologia e di Storia dell'Arte*. 9: 24-34. At 30 n.16 tav.11.3

Cordano, Federica 2005. Epigrafi. In Maniscalco, Laura(eds.), *Museo Civico "Corrado Tamburino Merlini" di Mineo: sezione archeologica*. Mineo. pp. 119-125. At 121

Cordano, F. 2014. Materiale vecchio e nuovo dalla Sicilia orientale. In Alfieri Tonini, T., Struffolino, S.(eds.), *Dinamiche culturali ed etniche nella Sicilia orientale dall'età classica all'epoca ellenistica*. Trento. pp. 105-111. At 107-108 no.6

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